

Diterpenoid quinones and other constituents from the roots of *Clerodendron tomentosum* R. Br.

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Abstract : Chemical investigation of combined pet. ether and benzene fractions from the ethanolic extract of *Clerodendron tomentosum* R. Br. afforded three diterpenoid quinones, viz. 12-acetylroyleanone, royleanone and 6,7-dehydroroyleanone along with *n*-hexacosane, eicosanoic acid, (24S)-ethylcholesta-5,22,25-triene-3 β -ol, α -amyrin and oleanolic acid. This is the first report of the isolation of diterpenoid quinones from this plant, also 12-acetylroyleanone has been obtained for the first time from a natural source.

Keywords : *Clerodendron tomentosum*, diterpenoid quinones, 12-acetylroyleanone, triterpenoids.

Introduction

Clerodendron tomentosum R. Br. is a well known ornamental plant (Family : Verbenaceae) found throughout India¹. A survey of literature revealed only one reference on the chemical investigation of this plant reporting the isolation of aliphatics, sterols and triterpenoids from the leaves and stem². Keeping this observation in view, the present work dealing with the isolation of constituents from the pet. ether and benzene fractions of the alcoholic extract of roots was undertaken.

The roots of *C. tomentosum* R. Br. were collected from Agricultural Research Station, Durgapura, Jaipur and identified for authenticity in the Department of Botany, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur (Herbarium Sheet No. RUBL 19904). Shade dried and coarsely powdered roots (3.5 kg) were extracted exhaustively with ethanol (95%) on a steam bath for 3 \times 8 h. The extract was concentrated under reduced pressure when a dark brown solid (100 g) was obtained. The ethanolic extract was then fractionated with pet. ether followed by benzene. The dark brown pet. ether fraction (7 g) and benzene fraction (13 g) were concentrated under reduced pressure. As both the fractions showed similar TLC profile (benzene : ethyl acetate, 1 : 1), they were mixed together and chromatographed over silica gel which on elution with solvents of increasing polarity afforded eight compounds

including three diterpenoid quinones, two waxy components and three triterpenoids. The diterpenoid quinones are rarely occurring natural compounds and found to exhibit anticancer activity³.

12-Acetylroyleanone : Elution with pet. ether yielded an orange semi-solid which on crystallization afforded orange needles (2-butanone), m.p. 170–172 °C, C₂₂H₃₀O₄. The UV absorption peaks at 283, 289 and 405 nm indicated the presence of quinonoid nucleus in the compound⁴. It exhibited IR peaks at 1670, 1640 (quinone ring), 1750, 1250 cm⁻¹ (acetyl group). Its ¹H NMR spectrum displayed signals at δ 0.89, 0.93 and 0.98 (tertiary methyl groups), 1.02 (doublet) and 3.20 (multiplet) for isopropyl group, 2.17 (singlet) for acetyl group, 1.81, 2.15, 2.67, 2.76 (triplets), 2.35 (multiplet) for methylene and 2.91 (triplet) for methine protons. Its mass spectrum showed molecular ion peak at *m/z* 358 [M⁺] and other significant peaks at 330 [M⁺-CO], 315 [M⁺-COCH₃], 302 [M⁺-2CO], 272, 260, 232, 189, 176, 146, 84, etc. The compound on alkaline hydrolysis gave orange needles (pet. ether), m.p. 178–180 °C, C₂₀H₂₈O₃ [M⁺ 316] which was identified as royleanone.

The mother liquor after isolation of 12-acetylroyleanone was rechromatographed over a silica gel column and eluted with hexane followed by hexane-benzene mixture. The

6,7-Dehydroroyleanone

eluent with hexane : benzene (1 : 1) was crystallized with pet. ether, when a mixture of orange needles and orange powder was obtained which were separated mechanically and identified as royleanone and 6,7-dehydroroyleanone respectively.

Royleanone : It was obtained as orange needles, m.p. 178–180 °C, $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_3$ [M^+ 316]. In the UV spectrum, peaks at 403, 283 and 277 nm indicated quinonoid skeleton⁴. It was identified by comparison of IR, ^1H NMR and mass spectrum with that of 12-acetylroyleanone and co-TLC and co-IR with an authentic sample⁵.

6,7-Dehydroroyleanone : It was obtained as orange powder, m.p. 160–162 °C, $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_3$ [M^+ 314], also characterized on the basis of comparative ^1H NMR with royleanone where two additional double doublets in the downfield region at δ 6.82 (J 9.9, 3.3 Hz) and 6.47 (J 9.9, 3.7 Hz) were obtained indicating the presence of a double bond in conjugation with the benzene ring.

The other components viz. hexacosane⁶, eicosanoic acid⁶, (24*S*)-ethylcholesta-5,22,25-trien-3 β -ol⁷, α -amyrin⁸ and oleanolic acid⁹ were identified by comparison of physical and spectral data.

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